

ASSESSING LASER TRACKER ACCURACY WITH VARIOUS MOUNTING SYSTEMS

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Abstract

In today's era, due to the 4th Industrial Revolution, the need for quick and accurate measurements is huge. Their application in a variety of industrial applications has led to the established use of laser trackers, for measuring, aligning and verifying dimensions in large constructions or objects with complex geometry. Laser trackers are portable coordinate measuring systems which use laser technology to measure points in three dimensions with accuracies in the range of micrometers. In order to receive extremely precise measurements, plenty of operational tests must be taken before starting the measuring process. These tests include angular accuracy, absolute distance or level checks, and must be performed in specific test fields, according to the manufacturers.

In this research work, after creating the appropriate test fields, the necessary operational checks of the Vantage Faro Laser Tracker took place. Each of them is described and performed in detail, using five different laser trackers' mounting systems. In order to use different mounting systems, a special adapter has been created for the specific model of Vantage Faro laser tracker.

So, the main purpose of this study is to examine how these mounting systems may respond to these tests and if the achieved accuracy by using them is consistent with the specifications of the laser tracker.

Key Words: laser tracker, mounting systems, compensation, operational checks

Περίληψη

Στις μέρες μας (2025), λόγω της 4ης Βιομηχανικής Επανάστασης, η ανάγκη για γρήγορες και ακριβείς μετρήσεις είναι τεράστια. Η εφαρμογή τους σε μια ποικιλία βιομηχανικών χρήσεων έχει οδηγήσει στη καθιερωμένη χρήση των laser trackers, για τη μέτρηση, την ευθυγράμμιση και την επαλήθευση διαστάσεων σε μεγάλες κατασκευές ή αντικείμενα με πολύπλοκη γεωμετρία. Οι laser trackers είναι φορητά συστήματα μέτρησης συντεταγμένων που χρησιμοποιούν τεχνολογία λέιζερ για τη μέτρηση σημείων σε τρεις διαστάσεις με ακρίβεια της τάξης των μικρομέτρων.

Για την επίτευξη εξαιρετικά υψηλής ακρίβειας μετρήσεων, απαιτείται η διεξαγωγή πολλών λειτουργικών ελέγχων πριν την έναρξη της μετρητικής διαδικασίας. Αυτοί οι έλεγχοι περιλαμβάνουν τη γωνιακή ακρίβεια, τον έλεγχο ADM και τον έλεγχο των ισοσταθμητών και πρέπει να πραγματοποιούνται σε συγκεκριμένα πεδία δοκιμών, σύμφωνα με τις προδιαγραφές των κατασκευαστών.

Στην παρούσα εργασία, αφού δημιουργήθηκαν τα κατάλληλα πεδία δοκιμών, πραγματοποιήθηκαν οι απαραίτητοι έλεγχοι του Vantage Faro Laser Tracker. Καθένας από

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αυτούς περιγράφεται και εκτελείται λεπτομερώς, χρησιμοποιώντας πέντε διαφορετικά συστήματα στήριξης του laser tracker. Για τη χρήση διαφορετικών συστημάτων στήριξης, δημιουργήθηκε ένας ειδικός προσαρμογέας (adapter) για το συγκεκριμένο μοντέλο του Vantage Faro Laser Tracker.

Έτσι, ο κύριος σκοπός αυτής της μελέτης είναι να εξετάσει πώς ανταποκρίνονται αυτά τα συστήματα στήριξης στις δοκιμές και εάν η ακρίβεια που επιτυγχάνεται με τη χρήση τους είναι σύμφωνη με τις προδιαγραφές του laser tracker.

1. Introduction

The 4th Industrial Revolution revolutionized industries in the modern era by introducing advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things (IoT), and automation. High-precision measurement in such a rapidly changing world has become more crucial than ever. The aerospace, automotive, and heavy machinery sectors, for example, rely on accurate measurement equipment to deliver quality control, alignment, and verification of enormous constructions or complex geometrical figures (Lau et al. 1986).

Among these tools, laser trackers (LTs) are gaining more significance since they are portable and extremely accurate. Laser trackers take measurements of coordinates in three dimensions with micrometer accuracy through the use of laser technology, and therefore they are indispensable for industrial purposes that require accurate measurements.

Though they are extremely accurate, the performance of laser trackers can be influenced by numerous factors, such as the mounting systems used during measurement. While operation requirements can require the use of special mounting systems for the purposes of stability and precision, there is an interest in knowing whether partially modified mounting systems can be combined with the standard ones. The purpose is to find out if the combined mounting systems will provide stability without affecting measurement accuracy. Therefore, understanding how different mounting configurations affect laser tracker performance is important in ensuring precise measurement results.

The goal of the research is to examine the effect of five mounting systems, in the working precision of the Vantage Faro Laser Tracker, in comparison with the reached accuracy the values provided by manufacturer specifications through special checks offered by the manufacturer.

The mounting system which is delivered from Faro is rather specific and for it to be possible to operate the Laser Tracker with various mounting systems an adapter has been constructed in a manner to be put inside any normal tribrach. The origin of this job came about because of the need to put the instrument at a significantly lower height compared to that offered by the industrial tripod.

The findings of the current research will provide valuable insight into how normal and altered mounting systems influence the performance of the Faro Laser Tracker. The findings will make industrialists decide appropriate mounting options, enhance reliability in measurements, and optimize quality control processes.

This paper consists of the following 4 sections. The first one contains a literature review – concerning laser trackers, mounting systems, and measurement accuracy affecting factors. The second is the methodology which describes the field test procedures, the mounting adapter that have been created, and the five mounting systems.

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The third part “Results and Analysis” presents the data that have been collected and the statistical analysis after the operational checks. Finally, the last section “Discussion” describes the findings, highlighting the key findings for the stability of the examined mounting systems.

2. A Brief Literature Overview

Laser trackers are precision coordinate measuring machines that employ a laser beam in tracking a retroreflective target, commonly a spherically mounted retroreflector (SMR) (Lau et al. 1986). Three-dimensional coordinates are calculated from relating distance and angular measurements with laser tracker accuracy typically in the micrometer range. The laser tracker was invented in the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) mid-1980s.

In their seminal work on LTs, they explain the technology and some of the sources of error, thus providing tips to users on how to test them. There have been numerous studies since, documenting various LT error sources. Some of these works are listed in Wang et al. (2020).

One of the causes of error is the mounting system that is necessary to ensure the stability and reliability of laser trackers. A study by Boruchowski and Piszak (2022) describes that even minor vibrations in the mounting setup can cause significant errors in the measurements taken. Manufacturers typically advise accurate mounting systems particular to their laser trackers to minimize such risks (FARO, 2025).

Nevertheless, recent studies have explored the potential of modifying mounting systems. Different applications require different mounting options for the laser tracker system in terms of requirements for portability, stability, spatial restrictions, work safety etc. (Saure et al. 2022).

The sensitivity of the laser tracker requires a close examination of the stability of their mounting systems. To minimize such issues, due care should be taken so that the mounting system is robust and minimizes external disturbance. Through the use of best practices such as sufficient warm-up time for the laser tracker to become thermally stable, measurement precision can be enhanced (FARO, 2025).

Thus, considering the sensitivity of the FARO Vantage Laser Tracker, the construction of an adapter to mount it on various support systems (centering bases, tripods) with the aid of a tribrach is a viable idea. The presence of stable, non-vibrating support is paramount to guaranteeing the accuracy of the measurements.

3. Methodology

3.1 Description of the Vantage Faro Laser Tracker

The FARO Vantage Laser Tracker is a portable, accurate 3D coordinate-measuring instrument with a measuring distance of up to 80 m (262 ft). It consists of a Laser Tracker Measuring Head and a Master Control Unit (MCU). The Measuring Head measures the location of a Spherically Mounted Retroreflector (SMR) target by employing a laser to determine its coordinates by taking two angles (azimuth and zenith) and radial distance with the TruADM system (FARO, 2016).

The key features include:

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- Instant-on laser for quick start-up
- MultiView Cameras for quick target reacquisition
- Built-in weather station and high-precision level sensor
- IP52 rating for durability against dust and water
- Lightweight design for easy mounting and repositioning

MCU is linked to the Measuring Head via a 3 m (9.8 ft) cable, which is expandable to 10 m (32.8 ft). The Vantage is particularly designed for industrial and field applications requiring high-accuracy measurements.

The accuracy for the Vantage per the ASME B89.4.19 - 2006 Standard is expressed as Maximum Permissible Error (MPE). Typical performance is half the MPE values, and it follows linear relationship with distance (L) between the laser tracker and the prism. So, the MPE for the Absolute Distance Meter (ADM) is $16\mu\text{m} + L \cdot 0.8 \mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ and for the Transverse $20\mu\text{m} + L \cdot 5 \mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ (FARO, 2016).

3.2 The general workflow of the operational checks of Vantage Faro Laser Tracker

The FARO software provides interim tests that allow the quick assessment of the system's pointing accuracy, ADM accuracy and precision level accuracy. It also provides compensation routines to adjust parameters that compensate the Laser Tracker Measuring Head's pointing accuracy. During all tests and compensations, the software compares the results to the Maximum Permissible Error (MPE) of the Vantage per the ASME B89.4.19 Standard. The general workflow of these tests is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The workflow of the operational checks

This group of checks should be performed before every measurement session or if the temperature has changed by more than around 2.8°C , and it may be especially required after the Laser Tracker System has been shipped or subjected to an impact.

A prerequisite for running the above workflow is the running of the StartUp Checks, within which the Initialization of the instrument is also carried out. In this case, the position-sensing detector and the angular encoders are initialized. Thermal stabilization within the StartUp Checks may take more than 40 minutes.

In Chapter 4, each of the checks shown in the workflow chart will be discussed in detail in the measurement stages. Here, there will be a brief description of what is achieved after each check is completed, according to the system's user manual (FARO, 2016).

The user of the system must first perform the Angular Accuracy Check, wherein the SMR is measured in frontside and backside orientations, and the difference between the angular components of the two readings ("Backside Error") is ascertained. This ascertained value ("measured error") is then compared to the Maximum Permissible Error (MPE) for the specific Faro Laser Tracker Vantage specifications according to the ASME B89.4.19 Standard. If the measured error exceeds the MPE, the user must perform the Quick Compensation Check. Otherwise, the system is ready for use and meets the manufacturer's specifications (FARO, 2016).

Quick Compensation is a routine that corrects angular measurement errors. It is a single-point compensation and the fastest method to compensate the Laser Tracker System. The process completion time for this process is from 2 to 5 minutes. If this check is fine, the system is ready for use. Otherwise, the user must proceed with the Pointing Compensation check.

This routine is the most accurate method of identifying and compensating for the backsight error. This routine, in contrast to the Quick Compensation, requires more space and time to execute. At this point, it should be noted that the user manual states that the routine has three sub-routines. Observe that the name of the main routine and one of its sub-routines are identical (Pointing Compensation) according to the Faro user manual (FARO, 2016).

- Pointing Interim Test: An interim test of the Angular Accuracy or backsight error at a number of points throughout the working volume of the Laser Tracker Measuring Head. If the test fails, the Pointing Compensation sub-routine must be performed.
- Pointing Compensation: This test is intended to improve Angular Accuracy as a function of radial distance increasing from the Laser Tracker Measuring Head. If the test fails, the Axis Non-Squareness Compensation sub-routine must be performed.
- Axis Non-Squareness Compensation: This step involves additional measurements that can be used to further improve Angular Accuracy. These measurements are designed to improve Angular Accuracy as the Zenith axis of the Laser Tracker Measuring Head changes.

As a final step, it is recommended to repeat the initial Angular Accuracy Check to ensure that the compensation parameters have been correctly updated in the Laser Tracker System.

3.3 Special support system (adapter) for the laser tracker

It is recommended in the system's official operator manual to place the Laser Tracker on a screwable mandrel (Figure 2a), mounted using a 3.5"-8 UN-2B threading pattern with the aid of the FARO industrial tripod or an equivalent mounting system.

To make the mounting of the mandrel on support systems aside from the FARO industrial tripod easier, the adapter shown in Figure 2b was conceptualized. One side can be screwed

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with the mandrel, and the other side of the adapter can be screwed into a tribrach adapter (5/8 inch). One must take care that the tribrach adapter (Figure 2c) is attached so that it cannot be rotated. If it happens to be a rotatable one, then rotation must be restrained or prevented. Otherwise, rotational motion of the instrument in a back-and-forth direction (frontside/backside) may also turn the base.

Figure 2. (a) Screwable mandrel. (b) Adapter. (c) Tribrach adapter.

3.4 The five mounting systems under check

The five different support systems that were tested are presented in Figure 3 and they were a wooden tripod, an aluminum tripod, a Leica Heavy-duty tripod, a FARO heavy-duty tripod and a Centering base.

Figure 3. (a) Wooden tripod. (b) Aluminum tripod. (c) Heavy duty tripod (Leica). (d) Heavy duty tripod (FARO). (e) Centering base.

To use the above support systems, a tribrach, a tribrach adapter and the constructed adapter (Figure 2-Section 3.3) were required.

4. The test fields of the operational checks

For the aforementioned support systems, the operational checks were performed to determine whether they can provide sufficient stability to deliver the required measurement accuracy while using the Laser Tracker. The following section will provide a detailed description of the control fields required for each check illustrated in the workflow diagram in Figure 1.

Angular Accuracy Checks: This test requires a Spherically Mounted Retroreflector (SMR) and a stable nest to hold the SMR. A second heavy-duty telescopic tripod was used to hold

the SMR nest for this purpose. When the nests are unstable when taking the measurement or the mounting system of the Laser Tracker is unstable, the Angular Accuracy test will fail or the results will be poor. For the check, the procedure starts with the user placing the SMR in the Home position of the tracker. After measuring this point, the user must place the SMR at the subsequent three points in 3D space: $AZ= 90^\circ$, $Ze= 90^\circ$, $D= 6000$ mm / $AZ= -45^\circ$, $Ze= 90^\circ$, $D= 2000$ mm / $AZ= 45^\circ$, $Ze= 135^\circ$, $D= 2000$ mm

Quick Compensation: This test field is easy. The user must place the SMR in the Home position of the tracker and then move it to any preferred location, typically in the working area of the specific task. This process takes approximately five minutes to complete.

Pointing Interim Test: This test employs a routine similar to the Angular Accuracy Test. This routine consists of Home position measurements and measurements at the below 3D space points: $AZ= 90^\circ$, $Ze= 90^\circ$, $D= 6000$ mm / $AZ= -45^\circ$, $Ze= 90^\circ$, $D= 2000$ mm / $AZ= 45^\circ$, $Ze= 135^\circ$, $D= 2000$ mm / Any user-defined points in addition to those above

Pointing Compensation: Pointing Compensation routine requires measurements in the Home position and the subsequent SMR locations: Any azimuth, $Ze= 90^\circ$, $D= 2000$ mm / $D= 3600$ mm / $D= 5200$ mm / $D= 6800$ mm / $D= 8400$ mm / $D= 10000$ mm

Axis Non-Squareness Compensation: This process begins with a measurement at Home position, and subsequently measurements are recorded at the following locations: $AZ= 0^\circ$, $Ze= 135^\circ$, $D= 2000$ mm / $AZ= 0^\circ$, $Ze= 110^\circ$, $D= 4000$ mm / $AZ= 0^\circ$, $Ze= 110^\circ$, $D= 4000$ mm / $AZ= 0^\circ$, $Ze= 110^\circ$, $D= 6000$ mm

ADM Check: ADM Check is one of the toughest test areas. For this test, a bar (Figure 4a) to which two SMR nests are mounted two meters apart is used. In this setup, the bar is oscillated between two positions while the Laser Tracker Measuring Head remains stationary.

- First position: The Measuring Head of the Laser Tracker is set three meters away from the tracker (Figure 4b, Left).
- Second position: The Laser Tracker is positioned along the measurement points line. The distance from the first point to the Measuring Head is 1 or 2 meters (Figure 4b, Right).

Level Check: The Level Check requires no special test field as it does not include the use of SMRs. The Laser Tracker Measuring Head must be mounted on a firm stand in the vertical position and leveled with the Electronic Bubble Level of the Laser Tracker.

Figure 4. (a) Used Bar. (b) ADM Check's positions.

5. Results

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The tests were conducted on February 22, 2025, for the Faro Laser Tracker with serial number VO1001405182 in the metrology control room of the School of Rural and Surveying Engineering – Geoinformatics Engineers, under specific meteorological conditions. The Air temperature was 17.35°C and the Air pressure was 757.75 mmHg.

The evaluation of the support systems began with the Faro industrial tripod, which was also used for the initial instrument compensation since it is the manufacturer’s recommended support system for ensuring the device operates according to specifications. Since this was the first tested system, the entire workflow from Figure 1 was performed. The required accuracy thresholds (MPE) set by the manufacturer were not met, particularly in angular measurements. The Angular Accuracy Check failed (Table 1) as two of the measured points were outside the permissible tolerances. Thus, the Quick Compensation was performed, with its parameters shown in the table below. However, even after applying the Quick Compensation (Table 2), the measured points did not pass the statistical validation checks.

Table 1. Angular Accuracy Check Results

Point	Az (°)	Ze (°)	D (mm)	Tolerance (mm)	Deviation (mm)	In Tolerance
1	91	91	6030	0.100	0.181	No
2	-49	94	1991	0.060	0.076	No
3	46	131	2191	0.062	0.050	Yes
4	127	92	2564	0.066	0.020	Yes

Table 2. Quick Compensation Results

	RX (rad)	RY (rad)
Before	-0.001198	-0.000081
After	-0.001197	-0.000084
Change	0.000002	-0.000003

The same issue occurred with the Pointing Interim Test (Table 3), which was performed immediately after the Quick Compensation.

On failure of Pointing Interim Test, following the workflow was the Pointing Compensation, which ultimately managed to achieve the needed angular accuracy of the Laser Tracker. Results of successful achievement of angular accuracy for this specific Laser Tracker are given in Table 4.

Table 3. Pointing Interim Test Results

Point	Az (°)	Ze (°)	D (mm)	Tolerance (mm)	Deviation (mm)	In Tolerance
1	91	91	6030	0.100	0.163	No
2	-49	94	1991	0.060	0.066	No
3	46	131	2191	0.062	0.047	Yes
4	127	92	2564	0.066	0.005	Yes

Table 4. Pointing Compensation Results

Point	Az (°)	Ze (°)	D (mm)	Tolerance (mm)	Deviation (mm)	In Tolerance
1	112	91	1957	0.060	0.004	Yes
2	112	90	3719	0.077	0.009	Yes
3	112	90	5251	0.093	0.012	Yes
4	115	90	6722	0.107	0.015	Yes
5	115	90	8412	0.124	0.018	Yes
6	111	90	10065	0.141	0.024	Yes

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Optionally, even though the Pointing Compensation check was successfully completed, the user may choose to perform the Axis Non-Squareness Check. The check was successful, and the calculated parameters are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Axis non-squareness Compensation Results

	RX (rad)	RY (rad)	CTX (m)	CTY (m)
Before	-0.001197	-0.000084	0.000019	0.000459
After	-0.001190	-0.000080	0.000008	0.000463
Change	0.000007	0.000004	-0.000010	0.000005

In the case of the Faro industrial tripod support system, the last two recommended checks, the Level Check and the ADM Check, by the manufacturer, were both performed. The outcome of these two checks is not related to that for the angular accuracy. The outcome of the checks is given in Tables 6 and 7.

Table 6. Level Checks Results

Point	Level Movement (arcsec.)	Difference(arcsec.)	MPE(arcsec.)	In Tolerance
1	360.44	0.44	2.00	Yes
2	360.92	0.92	2.00	Yes
3	360.29	0.29	2.00	Yes
4	359.79	-0.21	2.00	Yes
5	359.51	-0.49	2.00	Yes

Table 7. ADM Checks Results

Measured Distance (m)		Difference (μm)	Compined MPE (μm)	Result
Station 2	Station 1			
1.3058497	1.3058595	10	69	Pass

After completing the Laser Tracker check using the Faro industrial tripod as the support system, the industrial tripod from Leica company was tested, in combination with the use of a tribrach, a tribrach adapter, and the adapter created to mount the mandrel. It was found that the stability required for the Laser Tracker with this support system was ensured. Since the Laser Tracker had already undergone compensation with the previous support system, the Angular Accuracy Check was successfully completed this time. As a result, the entire workflow did not need to be followed, and only the ADM Check was performed next. Since this particular tripod is telescopic, the check was successfully carried out twice: once when the Laser Tracker was at a height of approximately 1.5 m (Tables 8 & 9) and again at a height of 2.3 m.

Table 8. Angular Accuracy Check Results at 1.5m height

Point	Az ($^{\circ}$)	Ze ($^{\circ}$)	D (mm)	Tolerance (mm)	Deviation (mm)	In Tolerance
1	86	91	6012	0.100	0.059	Yes
2	-46	93	2075	0.061	0.042	Yes
3	41	136	2200	0.062	0.046	Yes
4	127	94	4200	0.082	0.056	Yes

Table 9. ADM Check Results at 1.5m height

Measured Distance (m)		Difference (μm)	Compined MPE (μm)	Result
Station 2	Station 1			
1.3059242	1.3059087	15	69	Pass

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The third support system used was the centering base, in combination with the tribrach, the tribrach adapter, and the adapter created to mount the mandrel. The Angular Accuracy Check was successfully completed, and the results are presented in Table 10.

Table 100. Angular Accuracy Check Results

Point	Az (°)	Ze (°)	D (mm)	Tolerance (mm)	Deviation (mm)	In Tolerance
1	91	89	6005	0.100	0.080	Yes
2	-41	86	2131	0.061	0.050	Yes
3	47	131	2001	0.060	0.026	Yes
4	146	94	6267	0.103	0.048	Yes

Table 111. ADM check Results

Measured Distance (m)		Difference (μm)	Compined MPE (μm)	Result
Station 2	Station 1			
1. 3059291	1. 305908	20	69	Pass

For the two tripod support systems (wooden and aluminum), it was not possible to perform the measurement. The motors of the Laser Tracker caused micro-vibrations in the tripods, making measurements impossible. The process for both tripods started with the Angular Accuracy Check, and it was only possible to measure the first two points with ($Z_e = 90^\circ$). The third point with ($Z_e = 135^\circ$) could not be measured in either case, as the instrument displayed the error message “Repeatability Check Failed”, preventing the completion of the check.

6. Conclusions

The study aimed to contrast the impact of different mounting systems on the accuracy and stability of the FARO Vantage Laser Tracker during working inspections. Following extensive testing, the following conclusions were drawn:

➤ Effectiveness of Manufacturer-Recommended Mounting Systems

The FARO industrial tripod, which was specially designed for the laser tracker, provided firm support and attained the required levels of accuracy following compensations as necessary. The second industrial tripod, utilizing the custom adapter, also provided proper stability and facilitated successful measurement.

➤ Performance of Alternative Mounting System

The centering base, with the custom adapter, was capable of maintaining measurements precise and was a working alternative to the recommended tripod from the manufacturer. Wooden and aluminum tripods were not suitable for laser tracker measurements. Their structural compliance and susceptibility to the tracker's motor vibration resulted in measurement failure, making them inappropriate for precision metrology applications.

➤ Need for Compensation Procedure

Despite the stability of the industrial tripod, initial tests revealed deviation beyond the Maximum Permissible Error (MPE). This highlights the necessity of performing compensation procedures before use, that is, Quick Compensation and Pointing Compensation. After applying these compensations, measurement precision improved substantially to meet manufacturer specifications.

7. Recommendations

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Assessing Laser Tracker Accuracy with Various Mounting Systems

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To give an accurate measurement, manufacturer-approved supporting systems should be used, such as the FARO industrial tripod or any high-stability support. Wood or aluminum tripods whose structural flexibility and susceptibility to vibration are not accurate enough to be used in accuracy measurements should never be used. Before measurements are made, compensation checks, i.e., Quick Compensation and Pointing Compensation, have to be carried out to eliminate systematic errors and achieve the intended accuracy. The stability of the mounting height has to be considered when using industrial tripods because minor variations in height do not significantly affect the accuracy, as long as the support system remains stable. In addition, future research should explore other mounting systems and evaluate the long-term performance of custom adapters in various industrial environments to make laser tracker installations more flexible and reliable.

References

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